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**DEPARTMENT OF LINGUISTICS
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A CRITICAL EVALUATION OF THE EFFECTIVENESS OF ENGLISH TEXTBOOK FOR TRIBAL STUDENTS IN MAHARASHTRA

Dr. Priti Bala Sharma, Assistant Professor, Amity School of Languages, Amity University

Abstract

Around Nine percent of India's population is constituted by Scheduled Tribes with 90.87% of them living in rural areas and 9.23% in urban areas. The diversity of this community due to its economic backwardness, geographical isolation, distinct culture, and aloofness from the society at large makes it weaker section of the society. Despite of many provisions in the constitution and tireless efforts of Government in the development of these Scheduled Tribes, the tribal children face many challenges and problems in education specially in learning English language as a foreign language. This paper aims to investigate the effectiveness of the English course book prescribed for the tribal students in Maharashtra. To investigate the effectiveness of the course book in teaching English, both qualitative and quantitative methods of data collection i.e. interviews, questionnaires and classroom observations are used.

Keywords: Tribal Students, EFL, Ashram Schools in Maharashtra, Source Culture Elements.

Introduction

The word 'Tribe' derives from the Latin word 'Tribus' meaning 'one-third'. It originally referred to one of the three territorial groups. Tribes or tribal groups are not defined anywhere in the constitution although Scheduled Tribes are represented as the tribe or tribal communities notified by the President in accordance with Article 342. The data¹⁴ reflects that around nine percent of India's population is constituted by Scheduled Tribes with 90.87% of them living in rural areas and 9.23% in urban areas. Even if they live in the same village, these tribal communities maintain exclusive identities. The diversity of this community due to its economic backwardness, geographical isolation, distinct culture, and aloofness from the society at large makes it weaker section of the society. Besides, the painful past of forced exodus, violence eruptions and state's counter-violence also attenuated the development of these tribal communities. Government's attempts to integrate tribal communities with the mainstream society has rather scattered. The studies and reports (Apte and Lama 2008; Ministry of Tribal Affairs 2013) exemplify that the relocation of these tribal communities in the name of development has rather pushed them below poverty line and limited them to Vulnerable Tribal groups¹⁵.

¹⁴ India Educational Report, 2002 and Centre for Budget and Policy Studies (CBPS)

¹⁵ They were called Primitive Tribal Groups. They have extremely low literacy levels, decreasing population and 'pre-agricultural level technology. They were identified as having indications of primitive traits, distinctive culture; shyness of contact with the community at large; geographical isolation; and backwardness'. (Ministry of Tribal Affairs 2013)

It is evident that education is one of the basic factors in the integrated development of any culture and lack of basic needs and opportunities lead to intellectual deterioration of that culture or society.

The literature suggests that there are various internal and external factors such as frequent migrations of the tribes, economic and social background of the tribal families treating their children as unpaid labor force for household income and domestic chores, basic facilities in the schools, curriculum content, class, language issues, medium of instruction, and syllabus etc. that hamper the teaching learning process of these tribal students.

Therefore, on the basis of researches done on the internal factors affecting the learning of the tribal students, NPE (National Policy on Education) and POA (Programme of Action), 1992 acknowledged the importance of mother tongue for the instruction and the teaching material in their own language. Besides, many other measures have been taken by the government such as special residential schools like Ashram Schools with meals, uniforms, provision of providing free materials like textbooks, scholarships, and reservation of seats in state instructional institutions and employment agencies. The Parliamentary Standing Committee 2014 recommended the recruitments of trained teachers from tribal area and training for non-tribal teachers.

However, despite these policies, recommendations, and special provisions for tribal students, not much has been improved in the learning outcomes of the tribal students of India.

Methodology

Objective and Design of the Study

The objective of the present research is to investigate the cultural elements in course book of English for class VIII prescribed for Marathi Medium of students in Maharashtra, the effectiveness of the cultural content in the course book, and to examine the English teacher's conveyance of cultural elements in the course book.

Statement of the Problem

Cortazzi and Jin categorized three patterns or cultural aspects in an English course books. The first pattern mentions the learner's own culture/source culture, second pattern refers to the target culture and the third pattern excludes the first and second pattern of course books and give weightage to the international culture. In ESL class rooms, the amalgamation or the adequate weightage to all the three patterns of the course book is introduced and is successful. However, this pattern does not fit in to the category of tribal students of Ashram Schools of Maharashtra.

Therefore, this study focuses on the analysis of cultural elements in the course book of English prescribed for VIII standard for Marathi Medium students. The same book is prescribed¹⁶ for the tribal students studying in Ashram Schools of Maharashtra.

¹⁶ "The SSC Board, State Council of Education Research and Training (SCERT) and Bal Bharati (the state board for textbook publication)" design the curriculum and syllabus for the Maharashtra State Board. The same curriculum and syllabus is followed in the Ashram Schools in Maharashtra.

Rationale behind the Study

The reasons of tribal students' uninterestedness in learning English are multiple such as the poor economic, social and educational background of their parents, their limited exposure of English language, traditional syllabus, no authentic material, unavailability of technology and language lab, poor learning experiences in the classroom, improper infrastructure of classroom, and the alien cultural elements in the course books. As it has already been mentioned that for communicative competence in English language to the tribal students, their cultural aspects and local environmental aspects cannot be avoided. Therefore, it is a matter of observation as to how effective their course books are in terms of their cultural aspects.

Research Questions

This study focuses on the following questions:

1. To what extent the learners understand the course book i.e. the strength and weakness of the course book in terms of source cultural elements,
2. To what extent the course book is suitable for tribal students,
3. To what extent the course book caters to the needs of the tribal students,
4. To what extent the source cultural elements are available in content, illustrations, pictures, exercises, activities and homework in the course book,
5. To what extent teachers find the course book suitable for the tribal students in achieving the learning outcomes.

Hypothesis

It has been found in many researchers done on the course books analysis that local or source culture has its own importance in teaching learning of English language. The course books for English used by the tribal students in Maharashtra are planned, designed and prescribed by the Maharashtra State Board with SCERT and Bal Bharati for the dominant groups of English and Marathi medium students of Maharashtra. The changes were being made in the course books in recent years to introduce advanced teaching methodologies and conceptual learning. Nand Kumar, Principal Secretary of School Education Department, Maharashtra, said with reference to the course books of VII and IX,

"I wouldn't call it as a syllabus change but yes the textbooks are changing. The syllabus will be the same but the manner of teaching will change. We are moving away from rote learning to conceptual learning and overall, our textbooks should reflect the same. Hence it will be based on practical, experiential learning." (Digital Learning Magazine)

Now when the course books of Maharashtra State Board have undergone decisive changes, the question arises that whether they will achieve the learning outcomes for the tribal students or not as their exposure, experiences, and needs of English learning and course books is different than other urban and rural students from English and Marathi medium of Maharashtra. Therefore, it is proposed that the course book of English for Marathi Medium students used by tribal students of VIII class of Tribal Ashram Schools of Maharashtra should contain more elements from source culture than the target culture in order to achieve maximum learning outcomes from them for it is observed that out of eighteen chapters in

total, eleven chapters are based on target culture, six chapters have National culture and only one chapter can be considered under source culture category.

The Textbook under the Investigation

(<http://cart.ebalbharati.in/BalBooks/ebook.aspx>)

The course book for the present study is *My English Book English* currently prescribed for VIII class for Marathi Medium students and Tribal students of Tribal Ashram Schools of Maharashtra. The book is designed by Maharashtra State Bureau of Textbook Production and Curriculum Research, Pune. The Coordination Committee formed by GR No. Abhyas - 2116/(Pra.Kra.43/16) SD – 4 Dated 25.4.2016 has given approval to prescribe this textbook in its meeting held on 29.12.2017 from the Academic Year 2018-19.

Data Collection

The present study attempts to understand the effectiveness of the course book for the tribal students of Maharashtra with special reference to the elements of source culture in it. The course book is analyzed and questionnaire for both teacher and students of VIII class of a Tribal Ashram School in Mumbai region was prepared in order to examine the extent to which the source cultural elements in the course book fulfil the learning outcome.

Data Analysis

In order to achieve the purpose of the research, both quantitative and qualitative data is collected. The quantitative analysis consisted of questionnaire for students of VIII class from a Tribal Ashram School in Raigarh District of Mumbai. The rating had to be done on the basis of Understanding, Cultural elements in the chapter, Cultural elements in activities, and Cultural elements in homework in the course book, cultural elements in illustrations and pictures, and need of help book based on source culture for better learning outcome besides the course book. The questionnaire consisted of twenty questions based on the learners' cultural aspects like cultural values, cultural references through names, places, art, sports, festivals, food, ethics, fashion, etiquette etc. As not much work is done on the cultural elements in the English course books prescribed for tribal students of Tribal Ashram Schools of Maharashtra, therefore, questionnaire guidelines from two¹⁷ sources¹⁸ were studied and customized for this study.

¹⁷ Kilickaya - Guidelines to Evaluate Cultural Content in Textbooks (TESL/TEFL),

Besides, qualitative questionnaire was prepared and an interview was conducted with the teacher of English for VIII Class to get the in depth knowledge about his attitude, challenges and observation on the effectiveness of the course book and the elements of source culture in the course book. For this research, a tribal Ashram school in Wakdi village in Raigarh district of Mumbai was selected. The questionnaire was distributed to thirty students of VIII class and interview of the English Teacher of the class was taken.

Discussion and Finding

It is observed that the syllabus and course books prescribed for the students in Maharashtra are basically meant for two dominant groups' i.e English Medium students and Marathi Medium Students. The books have standard percentage of all the three cultural patterns i.e source, target and international culture. The tribal students from both urban and rural areas of Maharashtra are supposed to follow the same syllabus and course books prescribed to the dominant groups. It is found that tribal students cannot shake off their own culture and step in to the target or international culture easily due to various challenges or problems in terms of their social, economic, educational, and restricted exposures. Therefore, the source cultural elements become essential part of their course books.

In the course book under observation, the questionnaire for students highlighted these following aspects:

A. Understanding of the Course Book

Chart 1 reveals that 80% students can understand the book as far as the difficulty level of the course book is concerned. The teacher in the interview also explained that,

'The course books prescribed for Marathi Medium schools have less difficulty level than the course books prescribed for English medium and in Tribal Ashram Schools, the English course book for Marathi medium has been prescribed. Still I face problems in teaching this course book through English to these tribal students. In order to make my topic interesting and easy, I need to use local cultural and environmental examples in Marathi language'.

B. Cultural Elements in the Chapter

Chart 2 reveals that 79% of the students found the absence of source cultural elements in the course book where as 11% of the students found the source cultural elements excellent in the course book. It can also be said that majority of the class felt the source cultural to be a prominent part in understanding English better and require it. The elements includes names, places, cuisines, sports,

¹⁸ Al-Sofi, Bakr Bagash Mansour. "An Evaluation of the Cultural Aspects in the University English Textbook, Well Read 1.

weather/seasons, art, famous personalities, and festivals of source culture. Students found Places like Egypt, New York (My English book 76) and references of The Last Leaf, the Bay of Naples (My English Book 79), writers such as Douglas Malloch, Harry Behn, and names like Grace Darling, A.J. Cronin in the course book that they are not familiar with.

C. Illustrations and Pictures from Source Culture

Chart 3 illustrates that 83% students need more illustrations and pictures from source culture in the course book. The course book does not even include considerable pictures or illustrations of target and international culture. It is said that seeing is believing and the pictures and illustrations help the learners in story analysis, vocabulary, sentence structure and construction besides promoting and motivating the learners. Besides developing visual thinking and delivering fun, pictures and illustrations from source culture will help the tribal students in better understanding, connecting and building language skills.

D. Cultural Elements in Activities/ Exercises

Chart 4 indicates that 33% students found the source cultural elements weak in the activities or exercises in the beginning and end of the chapter whereas 30% students found the cultural elements excellent in the activities and exercises.

E. Cultural Elements in Homework

Chart 5 indicates that total 83% students could not find adequate homework questions based on their source culture or environment. In order to achieve learning outcome and retaining the knowledge given to them in the classroom, homework/ home assignment is very important. Home works are of various types such as Workbook based, extensive tasks, creative work, preparatory homework, integration homework, real world task, and project work. Importance of homework or home assignments for tribal students is significant as home or their hostel rooms are outside world and project work or real world tasks help them in achieving the communicative competence in real life context.

Findings

Adam Gonik said,

“We breathe in our first language, and swim in our second.”(Goodreads)

Most of the classrooms are course book dominated classrooms for the information and knowledge is imparted on the basis of the course book only. By integrating the source culture in content, ice breaking and brain storming exercises, activities, homework, and in

illustrations and pictures, the learning outcomes and better performance can be achieved and observed among the tribal students. As the teacher shared his suggestions in the interview,

These students have many challenges in learning English language such as impact of their friends, family members, and cooks in the schools who use mother tongue all the time. It limits their exposure to the target language and hampers their understanding and comprehension of English Language. The only source of learning the target language is their course book. Therefore, course book should have source cultural elements such as culture, values and customs of the tribal students that connect the learners with the target language through source culture. This course book has these elements, yet more familiar things should be included.

He further added, The teachers of Tribal Ashram schools have to undergo a training i.e. CHES. In this training they are trained to teach the course book by using different pedagogical methods and ICT, but the questions is how many teachers can implement these methods in the classrooms as there are many schools that lack basic facilities. Therefore, if a help book based on the familiar source culture of Maharashtra is supplemented with the course book, the desired learning outcomes can be achieved.

Conclusion

Tribal students from Tribal Ashram Schools of Maharashtra are different than other dominant groups of children in terms of their challenges and problems of learning English language. The conclusion is based on the data collected from one Tribal Ashram School in Raigrah district of Mumbai and the data analysis based on both quantitative and qualitative questionnaire distributed to the students. Firstly, it was observed that students understand the course book with the help of teacher's explanation of the content in their mother tongue. Secondly, the source cultural elements and values are there in the course book, but more familiar source culture, customs, and values need to be included in the form of content, pictures, illustrations, ice breaking sessions, exercise, activities, and homework. Thirdly, judicious use of mother tongue should be allowed for better understanding of the concepts. Fourthly, the need of supplementary authentic material is required in the form of help book. Fifthly, different teaching learning modules and training should be planned for teaching English to the tribal students of Ashram Schools, and sixthly bilingual dictionaries, and authentic material in the form of picture dictionaries, folk songs, folk stories, self-learning cards, peer learning, and glossary of English words with local dialects can be helpful in better comprehension of English Language.

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